

Machine Learning for Data Certification

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ABSTRACT

The data certification of the CMS experiment data is an essential process to guarantee high quality of the data for physical analysis. Up until now, it is being done by human experts for whom it is tedious and never ending task considering the volume of the CMS data. At its essence, it is binary classification problem of good quality data which contain signal of particle collision and bad data which are corrupted and contain weak or misleading background signal. Machine learning for data certification aims to automate this process and bring attention to phenomena which might have been missed by human inspection.

This work contributes towards the main project. The calculated statistics of the 2016 CMS dataset saved in root files are converted into NumPy arrays. Visual analysis of the features is performed and similarity metric is proposed to quantify potential discriminative power of different features.

The highly imbalanced distribution of classes in the data presents the major challenge of the problem. Experiments with a baseline neural network model showed that the majority classifier is learned almost instantly. Subsampling in order to obtain a balanced dataset show that the model performs poorly, comparable to the random classifier. The performance which was worse than random when the good data were in minority suggest that there are little to none consistent patterns in the bad data. Hence semi-supervised techniques appear to be promising option for better performance of the data certification process.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Compact Muon Solenoid (CMS) is large general-purpose particle detector on the Large Hadron Collider (LHC). The accelerated particles close to the speed of light collide in the centre of the CMS detector producing a fountain of other particles in all directions. CMS detector is made of many sensors which measures strength of a signal. For the analogue sensors the strength of the signal is interpreted as continuous value and for the digital sensors the signal is interpreted as 1 if the signal is strong enough (sensor was hit by a particle) and 0 otherwise. At each particle collision, the trigger decides if there was enough signal measured for further analysis. A specialized set of reconstruction algorithms is used for extracting particle tracks from the raw data. There are several stages of automatic decisions which filters the data and significantly reduces their volume.

Data Quality Monitoring (DQM) is a series of checks to validate the correctness of the data. Online DQM is done on the fly after each collision automatically. Offline DQM is the fine grain quality check performed on stored data. The last stage of the DQM process called Data Certification is done by human experts. Data which pass all the checks are certified as good for physics analysis. Data are certified as good if an expected performance is observed in all subsystem of the CMS detector.

Data Certification done by human experts is time consuming, tedious task. The principal aim of the project Machine learning for Data Certification (ML4DC) is to automate data certification process using machine learning techniques. The first benefit is in form of saved time of human experts. The second benefit is a potential for greater purity of the data because there is a limited number of variables a human is capable of checking manually, while a machine learning model can check all the relevant variables.

At an intermediate stage of the ML4DC development a goal is to automatically certify or automatically reject data for which a model has high certainty of the data being good and bad respectively. The data for which the model has low confidence would be flagged and passed to human expert for examination. A visual representation of the model's confidence of the data being good is shown in figure 1 in which the black zone represents bad data, the grey zone represents high uncertainty and the white zone represents good data. The aim is to shrink the grey region to minimum while maintaining high quality of data certification.

Figure 1 Confidence of the classification model, from left to right high confidence of data being bad to high confidence of data being good

The data certification task is challenging from machine learning perspective due to highly disproportional data set. A healthy data set contains on average only 2.5% of bad data and 97.5% of good data. Thus, high purity (only good data are certified) and high efficiency (all the good data are certified) of the classification are essential.

The process of extracting the data from CMS database and consecutive conversion into NumPy format is further discussed in section 2. The first examination of data in form of histogram plots per variable is discussed in section 3. Comparison of histograms of good and bad data is explained in section 4. A baseline artificial neural network model is described in section 5.

The project ML4DC is done in cooperation with Yandex School of Data Science.

2. ROOT TO NUMPY CONVERSION

In order to take an advantage of convenient processing in Python and wide availability of machine learning libraries the CMS data needs to be converted into Python friendly format, such as the NumPy arrays. The pipeline of obtaining the data is as follows: first a customised analyser extending Compact Muon Solenoid software (CMSSW) is used to extract data from the reconstructed datasets used for physics analysis and calculates a summary statistics. The summary statistics are calculated for each lumi-section and each variable and contain 7 values - mean, root mean square (RMS) and 5 quantiles. The calculated statistics are outputted as ROOT trees and stored in root files. A Python package “root_numpy” is used to work with ROOT trees within Python environment and converts it into NumPy arrays. These can be then saved by using native NumPy save function or using serialization Pickle package. Empirically it was found that native NumPy format is both faster and requires less than half of the storage space compared to Pickle format. Hence NumPy format was chosen.

A configurable Python script “tree_to_np.py” was implemented for conversion of large number of root files. The script takes as argument paths to the root trees and/or directories containing root trees (in which case it finds all the root files in all subdirectories) and outputs converted NumPy arrays into given destination path preserving the directories structure of the input directories. Optionally, the script can concatenate multiple root files into one NumPy array. This functionality is limited by the size of the RAM memory.

3. FEATURE EXAMINATION

From the 2016 data have been extracted data of approximately 2 million lumi-section (and it is still growing). These were stored into 54582 root files and then converted to the same number of corresponding NumPy arrays. There are 1,827,523 good lumi-section with the signal and 46,716 bad lumi-section, which accounts only for about 2.6%. 307,406 lumi-section have been filtered out either because their luminosity was too low, flag “lumi” was 0, (21,787) or at least one of the 400 chosen variables did not have expected 7 values and are considered corrupted (285,619).

For each lumi-section there are 410 variables. There are 400 variables containing 7 values each (mean,RMS and 5 quantiles) describing the distribution. The remaining 10 variables are of variable length and some of them are like a control variables - for example “isSig” is a ground truth flag from human experts marking if the lumi-section contains signal (good data) or it belongs to background (bad data).

Seven histograms of 100 bins are used to visualise a variable (one per each of its value). Figures 2 and 3 show histograms of variables “qMu5Eta” and “qPFJetPhi”. The histograms were made from JetHT primary dataset of 2016 data, containing 3328 background lumi-section and 139065 lumi-section with a signal. Both normal and background histograms have been normalised. The normal and background histograms of qMu5Eta variable are relatively different which means qMu5Eta would be a good discriminative feature. On the other hand, qPFJetPhi has the normal and background histograms almost completely overlaid, so it would not be possible to discriminate based on its values.

Figure 2 Histograms of the qMu5Eta variable. A similarity of good (normal) and bad (background) histograms is relatively low, indicating discriminative power

Figure 3 Histograms of the qPFJetPhi variable. A similarity of good (normal) and bad (background) histograms is relatively high, indicating low discriminative power

4. HISTOGRAM SIMILARITY

400 variables each containing 7 values results in 2800 plots. It is not feasible to examine all of them manually. Measuring a similarity or a distance between the signal distribution and background distribution provides a single value information on how discriminative the variable is. To compare the histograms a Bhattacharyya distance as defined in formula 1 is used.

$$\text{Bhattacharyya distance} = 1 - h_1 \times h_2$$

Formula 1 h_1 and h_2 are normalised histograms and “ \times ” is an element wise multiplication

The distance is a float between 0 and 1. The sorted distribution of distances between signal and background histograms for 2800 variables is shown in figure 4. For about 500 variables the distributions are almost identical for signal and background. Bhattacharyya distance is also shown in figures 2 and 3 in the legend of the plots.

Figure 4 Bhattacharyya distance between histograms of good and bad data for all 2802 features (400 variables x 7 features + 2 features)

5. BASELINE MODEL

A random classifier choosing between the two classes would be guess right label in half of the cases reaching accuracy 50%. An improvement on it (assuming that the training set is representative) is a majority class classifier which always predict the class which is the most frequent in the training set, then the accuracy is proportional to the majority class. In case of unbalanced dataset, like the one used for data certification, the accuracy could be high even without any proper learning. However, this does not solve the problem.

In all the subsequent experiments is used the JetHT primary dataset from 2016 CMS data and a simple two-layer neural network architecture. The neural network was built using Keras, the Python deep learning library. The input dimension was 2802 (7 time 400 chosen variables + crossSection and pathRates), the first layer had 1000 units, the second layer had 500 units, both layer had relu activation function and the sigmoid function was used at the output layer. As a loss function was chosen binary cross entropy and the optimizer used was adam. All the other parameters were left to Keras default values.

When using all the JetHT data the model very quickly, already during the first epoch of training, learns to predict the majority class only. This yields 98% accuracy, as there are only 2% of bad data in the JetHT dataset. In order to suppress the effect of unbalanced dataset, the class with good data was subsampled to match the amount of bad data. This has greatly reduced the size of the training data to only 4%. The accuracy reached with the balanced dataset was close to 50% suggesting that the model was unable to learn anything and is just guessing randomly.

Question posed was how much disproportion in the dataset is needed for the model to learn the majority class classifier. The amount of bad data in training data was kept fixed using all the bad data in the JetHT. The amount of good data was varied from only 1/10th (10%) of the bad data to 2.5 (250%) of the bad data. For each ration of the training data a separate model was trained.

The resulting accuracies are shown in figure 5. The results are very surprising especially for the ratios 0.1 to 0.9. The orange dots in the plot shows what would be accuracy of majority classifier for the given ratio of classes. For ratio 1:1 it is 50% (as mentioned above). When the ratio is growing to the right (there is more good data) the model learns immediately to predict majority class - everything predicted as good data (neural network accuracy is aligned with the majority class prediction). However, when the majority class is bad data (ration 0.1 to 0.9) the performance of the model deviates from the majority predictor and is even worse than random. Basically, the model learns to consistently predict only good data even when there is only few training examples of good data.

A possible explanation of this phenomenon is that while good data have consistent patterns, the bad data consist of varying anomalies which do not have any patterns. Thus, it is not possible to generalize over the bad data and as the bad data share some similarity with good data, the model learns to predict only the good.

Figure 5 Comparison of accuracies for varying amount of good training data using neural network classifier and majority classifier

6. FUTURE WORK

The next stages of the machine learning for data certification project consist of the classification model development, its adjustment to continuous operation and its integration into production. Due to likely lack of patterns in the bad data and the fact that they account only for 2 to 5% of the whole dataset it appears that semi-supervised model trained on one class only could bring good results. The underlying idea of the semi-supervised model is to train a robust model of the one class, the good data in this case, and then measure how well the new sample fits with the

model. If it fits it well, it would be classified as good, if it is anomalous it would be classified as bad.

Examples of semi-supervised models are autoencoders, isolation forest, and one class support vector machine. The autoencoder learns to reconstruct its input. If the reconstruction error is high, the sample is likely to be anomalous and thus corrupted. Both isolation forest, and one class support vector machine can predict score of how likely the given samples comes from the distribution on which they were trained. A threshold of the score can be set to distinguish good and bad data.

7. CONCLUSION

The data pre-processing stages which have been done before and as part of this project are necessary initial steps towards the ultimate goal of automatic data certification. This work built upon calculated summary statistics of the reconstructed 2016 CMS data which had been stored in root files. As part of this work, the whole 2016 dataset have been converted into NumPy arrays. A machinery for plotting of feature histogram was developed to ease the visual inspection of variables. Bhattacharyya distance was proposed as a mean of quantifying similarity/distance between the histograms of good and bad data. While experimenting with a simple neural network model and JetHT primary dataset it was confirmed that the model quickly learns the majority class of the imbalanced dataset. An unexpected behaviour was observed when the class of good data have been subsampled to the extent that it became minority class and the model instead of learning the new majority class (the bad data), still learnt to predict only the good labels which resulted in performance worse than random. This behaviour suggests that there are no consistent patterns in the bad data. Hence because of this and the highly imbalanced classes semi-supervised techniques relying on training on the data of one class only will be necessary in order to achieve performance with expected high purity and high efficiency of the classification. This conclusion is based on the experiments with JetHT primary dataset only and it remains to be confirmed whether this is dataset wide phenomenon.

8. APPENDIX

a. LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

LHC - Large Hadron Collider

CMS - Compact Muon Solenoid

CMSSW - Compact Muon Solenoid software

RMS - Root Mean Square

DQM - Data Quality Monitoring

ML4DC - Machine Learning for Data Certification

AOD - Analysis Object Data

b. LIST OF CHOSEN VARIABLES

This is the list of AOD collections from which the variables were calculated. From these collections were chosen physically motivated relevant variables. These were transverse momentum (Pt), Azimuthal angle (phi), Pseudo-rapidity (Eta), energy, charge, chi-squared, and for some collections some other specific variables.

PFJet, PFJet4CHS, PFJet8CHS, PFJetEI, PFJet8CHSSoftDrop, PFJetTopCHS, PFChMET, PFMET, CaloJet, CaloMET, CaloMETBE, CaloMETBEFO, CaloMETM, SuperCluster, SuperClusterhfEM, SuperCluster5x5, CaloCluster, CaloCluster5x5, Photon, gedPhoton, Muon, MuonCosm, MuonCosmLeg, GsfElectron, GsfElectronUncleaned, EBRecHitSource, EERecHitSource, ESRecHitSource, HBHERecHit, HFRecHit, HOREcHit, PreshowerClusterX, PreshowerClusterY

